

IMPORTANT ISSUES OF MODERN ENGLISH LEXICOGRAPHY

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Abstract: This article presents general theoretical views on lexicography. The basis of scientific research is dedicated to the problems of creating a dictionary, their solution, and issues such as their meeting in Uzbek lexicography are covered. It is devoted to the discussion of the difficult task of developing our own national dictionary corpus based on the experience of creating a base corpus in the study of the types of popular dictionaries in terms of structure.

Key words: lexicography, dictionaries, word meaning, descriptive material, compilers, frequency of meaning use.

The most urgent problems of lexicography are related to the selection of main words, the location and composition of word combinations, the principles of meaning definitions, and the semantic and functional classification of words. These problems are slowly being solved as the number of dictionaries and their types increases. The most important problems of modern lexicography are related to:

- 1) selection of lexical units;
- 2) location of selected lexical units;
- 3) adjusting the record;
- 4) selection and arrangement of word meanings;
- 5) definition of meanings;

6) visual material.

The problem of choosing lexical units. Selection of lexical units to add to dictionaries is one of the first problems facing the lexicographer. For this, the lexicographer takes into account the following:

- a) what types of lexical units are selected for inclusion;
- b) the number of these elements;
- c) what can be selected and what can be deleted in the dictionary;
- d) which form the dictionary should reflect, spoken or written, or both; e) whether the dictionary should contain obsolete units, technical terms, dialectisms, colloquialisms, etc.

The choice of different answer options from these ones depends on the type of dictionary, the purpose of the compilers (compiler), the future user of the dictionary, the size of the dictionary, the linguistic understanding of the dictionary compilers, and some other considerations. For example, Longman's Dictionary of Modern English (second ed. 1987), aims to provide advanced students and teachers of English with relevant information about the basic vocabulary of modern international English. Therefore, this dictionary contains about 56,000 words and phrases, including scientific and technical language, business and computer terms, literary words, informal and idiomatic usage. It mainly covers the main varieties of American and British English. Every time lexicographers release a new edition of Longman's Dictionary of Modern English (fifth edition, 2009), their goal is always the same: what can they do to make the dictionary a better support for English?

Inclusive units can be taken from other vocabularies or from reading material or speaking. For example, the New Oxford English Dictionary makes extensive use of the British National Corpus. (A corpus is a collection of language data collected for linguistic analysis). Location of lexical units. There are two ways of presenting records in alphabetical order and cluster type, that is, the included units

are divided into types based on one or another principle. For example, in synonym books, words are placed in synonym sets, and its main member acts as the head word of the entry. Entries can be grouped into word families with the same root, for example, with some common explanatory and translation dictionaries. Basic units are given as main entries appearing in alphabetical order, while words and phrases are given as suffixes or in the same entry as they appear in alphabetical order.

Record setting. Synchronous type is the most complex type of access in general explanatory dictionaries. In such dictionaries, the entry usually shows the following information: accepted spelling and pronunciation; grammatical features, including the part of speech of each input word, whether nouns are countable or uncountable, transitive/intransitive verbs, and grammatical forms; types of meaning; illustrative examples; phraseology; etymology; sometimes synonyms and antonyms. Compilers of the same type of dictionary can choose other settings of the standard entry: they can omit some elements or add others, choose a different arrangement of their location or a different way of presenting the same information. Compare entries in the Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners and the Longman Dictionary of Modern English.

Selection and arrangement of word meanings. There are three general ways to arrange word meanings:

- a) in historical order, that is, in the sequence of their historical development;
- b) in empirical or real order, that is, in accordance with the frequency of their use, that is, first with the most common meaning;
- c) in a logical order, that is, according to their logical connection.

In different dictionaries, the problem of arrangement is solved differently. For example, the general principle of meaning in the New Oxford English Dictionary is that every word has at least one primary meaning to which a number of secondary meanings can be attached. As lexicographers point out, core meanings

represent the common, central use of a word in Modern Standard English. It is accepted as the dominant meaning by native speakers. In most dictionaries, the meanings are usually arranged by frequency of use, but sometimes the primary meaning comes first, if this is the correct understanding of the derived (additional) meanings. if it is considered necessary for

Definition of meanings. The meaning of words can be determined in different ways: a) using only linguistic definitions related to words as speech material. They are used in most records;

b) with the help of encyclopedic definitions related to things that are the names of words; c) using synonymous words and phrases;

d) using references.

The choice of one or another type of definition, as a rule, depends on the nature of the word, that is, which part of the word it usually belongs to, the purpose and size of the dictionary. Encyclopedic definitions, for example, are specific to nouns, especially nouns and terms. They play a very important role in unabridged dictionaries. Synonyms are often used to define verbs and adjectives. In short dictionaries, they are usually used to save space. Cross-references are used to identify some abbreviations and variant forms.

Visual material. The presentation of visual materials depends on the type of dictionary and the goal set by the compilers (compiler). They can describe the first and last known occurrences of the input word, successive changes in its meaning, as well as graphic and phonetic forms, common words and combinations; they place words in context to determine their meaning and usage. Illustrative examples can be taken from various sources, such as classical or modern literature, or may be created by the compilers themselves.

In conclusion, the problems of lexicography still exist today, but the solution depends on the approach of the lexicographer. Dictionary definitions should give an idea of the truth expressed by the word and should be free from ambiguity.

When describing a word in a constructive dictionary, it is necessary to reveal the real semantic features under the lexical meaning of the word. Therefore, the interpretation of the lexical meaning of the word remains one of the most important theoretical issues of modern lexicography and semasiology.

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